

Methods For Assessing Reliability Growth Potential

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Abstract

The reliability growth potential for a system design is defined as the maximum system reliability that can be achieved for a particular management strategy. The management strategy determines which failure modes will or will not be fixed and the effectiveness of the fixes that are incorporated. In this paper we develop a practical methodology for estimating the growth potential for a system based on limited development testing data. In addition, confidence interval procedures associated with the realism of the requirement relative to the growth potential are discussed. These procedures are useful for evaluating the management strategy for a system and assessing the likelihood of attaining the reliability objectives. In addition, the methods are useful for trade-off studies establishing a management strategy early in a development program. Numerical examples are given in the paper illustrating the application of these procedures.

Introduction

The initial prototypes for a complex system will generally have reliability problems which must be found and fixed through a development testing program. Although the management strategy toward reliability growth may not be clearly defined or formally stated, it will in fact exist. The growth potential for a system design is defined as the maximum system reliability that can be achieved for a particular management strategy. Several elements of the overall management strategy determine the growth potential. First, the management strategy for the system places failure modes into two categories, Type A and Type B. Type A modes are all failure modes such that when seen during test, no corrective action will be taken. This accounts for all modes for which it is determined that it is not cost-effective to attempt to increase the reliability by a design change. Type B modes are all modes such that if seen, a design change or fix, will be attempted. Another element of the management strategy which impacts the growth potential is the effectiveness of the fixes for Type B modes. The maximum reliability that can be achieved for the system design and management strategy is attained when all Type B modes have been seen through testing and a fix, with a certain effectiveness, has been incorporated for each mode.

In terms of establishing attainable and cost-effective reliability requirements the following question is clearly important for reliability growth management: Does the growth potential exist for a system design and viable management strategies to attain the reliability requirements?

In this paper we give practical procedures to estimate the growth potential for a system based on test data and fix effectiveness and engineering experience. The approach focuses attention on the

impact of not fixing certain failure modes and quantifies the impact of the engineering fixes on the system growth potential. Based on the underlying model, the statistical confidence level associated with the reliability requirement being attainable (as compared to the growth potential) can be calculated for a system design and management strategy. From these results, alternate designs, such as high-reliability parts and redundancy for Type A modes, can be assessed along with evaluating other possible management strategies. If there is high risk associated with meeting the reliability objectives, then this may indicate a need to avoid a costly development testing program with the design. Examples illustrating these procedures are given in the paper.

Background

The notation and assumptions in this paper parallel those given in Reference 1.

It is assumed that all Type B modes are in series and fail independently according to the exponential distribution. We also assume that the occurrence of Type A modes follow the exponential distribution with failure rate λ_A . Fixes for Type B modes found during test may be incorporated into the system during test or incorporated as delayed fixes at the end of the test phase.

Let K denote the number of Type B modes in the system and let λ_i be the failure rate for the i -th Type B mode, $i = 1, \dots, K$. Then at time 0, the system failure rate $r(0)$ is

$$r(0) = \lambda_A + \lambda_B, \quad (1)$$

where $\lambda_B = \sum_{i=1}^K \lambda_i$. (In practice, of course, K will generally not be known before or after the testing.)

During test time $(0, t)$ a random number $M \leq K$ of distinct Type B modes will be observed. We further denote by d_i the effectiveness factor (EF) for the i -th Type B mode, $i = 1, 2, \dots, K$. The factor d_i is the percent decrease in λ_i after a corrective action has been made for the i -th Type B mode.

If corrective actions are taken on the M Type B modes observed by time t , then the system failure rate is reduced from $r(0)$ to

$$\begin{aligned} r(t) &= \lambda_A + \sum_{i=1}^M (1-d_i) \lambda_i + (\lambda_B - \sum_{i=1}^M \lambda_i) \\ &= \lambda_A + \lambda_B - \sum_{i=1}^M d_i \lambda_i. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

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The term

$$\sum_{i=1}^M (1-d_i) \lambda_i \quad (3)$$

is the failure rate for the M modes after the corrective actions. The term

$$(\lambda_B - \sum_{i=1}^M \lambda_i) \quad (4)$$

is the remaining failure rate for all unseen Type B modes.

All M Type B modes observed by test time t may not, of course, be fixed by time t so the actual failure rate at time t may not be r(t). However, r(t) can be viewed as the achieved failure rate at time t if all fixes were updated and incorporated into the system. See Figure 1.

Figure 1. Achieved Failure Rate if Observed Type-B Modes Receive Fix.

Estimation of r(t)

Before we consider the growth potential, we will first discuss estimation procedures for r(t). Suppose the system is tested for a test phase of length T and that all fixes for Type B modes found during test are incorporated as delayed fixes at the end of the test phase. This implies that the system failure rate is constant at $r(0) = \lambda_A + \lambda_B$ through the test phase and will then jump to a lower value r(T) after the delayed fixes have been implemented. See Figure 2.

Let N_A , N_B be the total number of Type A and Type B failures observed during the test (0,T) and let $N = N_A + N_B$. There are $M < N_B$ distinct Type B modes observed during the test. (A Type B mode is any mode that receives a fix at time T.) After the incorporation of the M fixes, the failure rate for the system at time T (after the jump) is given by the function r(T). See Figure 3.

Again, r(t) represents the system failure rate at time t if fixes for all Type B modes observed by time T are incorporated into the system with effectiveness factors d_i . The procedure for estimating r(t) is given in Reference (1) and is reviewed here.

Figure 2. Jump in System Failure Rate Due to Delayed Fixes.

Figure 3. Values of Failure Rate Before and After Delayed Fixes.

Let $E[.]$ denote expected value. In Reference (1) it is shown that

$$E[r(t)] = \lambda_A + \sum_{i=1}^K (1-d_i) \lambda_i + \sum_{i=1}^K d_i \lambda_i e^{-\lambda_i t} \quad (5)$$

It is also noted that under realistic assumptions,

$E[r(t)]$ may be expressed as

$$E[r(t)] = \lambda_A + \sum_{i=1}^K (1-d_i) \lambda_i + \mu_d h(t)$$

where μ_d is the mean effectiveness factor and $h(t)$ is the instantaneous rate with which a new Type B mode will occur at time t . A model of the form

$$h(t) = \lambda \beta t^{\beta-1} \quad (6)$$

is motivated from practical experiences in Reference [1].

Under the model an estimate $\hat{r}(t)$ for $r(t)$ is developed such that

$$E[r(t) - \hat{r}(t)] = 0. \quad (7)$$

That is, in this sense, $\hat{r}(t)$ is unbiased.

For Δt small, $h(t) \Delta t$ is interpreted as approximately the probability that a new, distinct Type B will occur in the interval, $(t, t + \Delta t)$. This is modelled as a non-homogeneous Poisson process. See Figure 4.

Figure 4. Intensity Function for Distinct Type-B Modes.

During testing over the interval $(0, T)$ system failures are observed at the N cumulative test times $y_1 < y_2 < y_3 < \dots < y_N$. Of the N_B Type B mode failures, M of these correspond to distinct Type B modes; the remainder are repeats. Let X_i be the y_j which corresponds to the cumulative time of the first occurrence of the i -th distinct Type B mode, $i=1, 2, \dots, M$. That is, X_1 is the cumulative test time of first occurrence of the first distinct Type B mode, X_2 is the cumulative test time of the first occurrence of the second distinct Type B mode, etc. We let N_i denote the total number of observed failures for the i -th distinct Type B mode.

For each of the M distinct Type B modes observed, d_i is the corresponding assigned effectiveness factors.

From Reference [1] the estimate of $h(t)$, given by equation (6) is

$$\hat{h}(t) = \hat{\lambda} \hat{\beta} t^{\hat{\beta}-1} \quad (8)$$

where

$$\hat{\beta} = \frac{M}{\sum_{i=1}^M \ln(T/X_i)} \quad (9)$$

and

$$\hat{\lambda} = \frac{M}{T^{\hat{\beta}}} \quad (10)$$

Let

$$\bar{d} = \sum_{i=1}^M d_i / M. \quad (11)$$

The failure rate $r(t)$ is then estimated, for $t > 0$,

by

$$\hat{r}(t) = N_A/T + \sum_{i=1}^M (1-d_i) N_i/T + \hat{d} \hat{h}(t). \quad (12)$$

In particular, for $t = T$, the end of the test phase,

$$\hat{r}(T) = N_A/T + \sum_{i=1}^M (1-d_i) N_i/T + \hat{d} \hat{h}(T). \quad (13)$$

Example

Suppose a system is tested for $T = 400$ hours with a total of 42 failures. Of the 42 failures 10 were Type A (due to modes that will not be fixed) and 32 were Type B (due to modes that will receive a fix). There are $M = 16$ distinct fixes; that is, 16 distinct Type B modes. Listed, in Table 1, for the 16 modes are the corresponding cumulative test times when they occurred. The first cumulative failure time for each of the 16 Type B modes is the time of occurrence of a distinct problem mode; that is, an X_i .

Table 1. Failure Times For Type B Modes

B Mode	Failure Times
1	15.04, 259.99
2	25.26, 120.89, 366.27
3	47.46, 350.2
4	53.96, 315.42
5	56.42, 72.09, 339.97
6	99.57, 274.71
7	100.31
8	111.99, 263.47, 373.03
9	125.48, 164.66, 303.98
10	133.43, 177.38, 324.96
11	192.66
12	249.15, 324.47
13	285.01
14	379.43
15	388.97
16	395.25

From these data we can determine:

X_i - cumulative time of first occurrence of the i -th distinct Type B mode.

N_i - total number of observed failures for the i -th distinct Type B mode.

For each observed Type B mode the X_i , N_i and assigned effectiveness factors (EF) d_i are listed in Table 2.

Table 2 First Occurrence, Number of Failures, and EF for the Observed Type B Modes

B Mode	X_i	N_i	d_i
1	15.04	2	.67
2	25.26	3	.72
3	47.46	2	.77
4	53.96	2	.77
5	56.42	3	.87
6	99.57	2	.92
7	100.31	1	.50
8	111.99	3	.85
9	125.48	3	.89
10	133.43	4	.74
11	192.66	1	.70
12	249.15	2	.63
13	285.01	1	.64
14	379.43	1	.72
15	388.97	1	.69
16	395.25	1	.46

The assignment of effectiveness factors should be based on historical experience and engineering considerations in regard to the proposed fixes.

From equations (9), (10) and (11) we have

$$\hat{\beta} = .797, \hat{\lambda} = .1350 \text{ and } \bar{d} = .721. \text{ This gives}$$

$\hat{h}(400) = .0319$. If all 16 fixes are incorporated into the system after the 400 hour test, and with the EF's given in the table, what is the new failure rate $r(T)$? To estimate this we use equation (13). The individual calculations are

$$N_A/T = 10/400 = .0250, \sum_{i=1}^{16} (1-d_i) N_i/T = .020$$

and $\bar{d} \hat{h}(400) = .0230$. This yields the estimate

$$\hat{r}(400) = .0250 + .020 + .0230 = .068, \text{ or a}$$

mean time between failure (MTBF) of 14.7.

The curve $r(t)$ given in Figure 3 depicts the system reliability expected at time t if fixes for all Type B Modes observed to time t are incorporated into the system. To estimate the function $r(t)$ for $t > 0$ we use

$$\hat{r}(t) = .0250 + .020 + .721 \hat{h}(t) \text{ where}$$

$$\hat{h}(t) = (.1350)(.797) t^{-.203}, t > 0. \quad (14)$$

Reliability Growth Potential

The failure rate $r(t)$ will depend on the management strategy which determines the classification of Type A and Type B modes and the engineering effort which determines the EF's. In addition, $r(t)$ depends on $h(t)$ which is the rate in which

problem failure modes are being seen during test. This rate drives the opportunity to see problems and, in turn, take corrective action, and, of course, is an important factor in the overall reliability growth rate. The reliability growth potential is the limiting value of $r(t)$ as t increases. This limit is the maximum reliability that can be attained with the management strategy. The maximum reliability will be attained when all K Type B modes have been observed and fixed with EF's d_i . In terms of failure rate, the growth potential is expressed by the equation

$$r_p = \lambda_A + \sum_{i=1}^K (1-d_i) \lambda_i \quad (15)$$

or, in terms of MTBF we have

$$M_p = 1/r_p. \quad (16)$$

Clearly, the management strategy can be changed to improved M_p . For example, Type A modes can be fixed to become Type B modes. High-Rel parts or redundancy for Type A modes could improve the design and reduce λ_A , and hence increase M_p . It is important, of course, to be able to estimate M_p so that the management strategy can be qualified, and appropriate trade-offs made.

Estimation of the Growth Potential

It is of interest to note that the first two terms in (5) for $E[r(t)]$ is the growth potential failure rate. We will also show that the first

two terms of $\hat{r}(t)$, namely

$$\hat{r}_p = N_A/T + \sum_{i=1}^M (1-d_i) N_i/T \quad (17)$$

is an unbiased estimate of the growth potential failure rate r_p . To see this, we observe that

$$\sum_{i=1}^M (1-d_i) N_i/T \quad (18)$$

can be written as

$$\sum_{i=1}^K (1-d_i) N_i/T \quad (19)$$

where, it is recalled, M is the observed number of Type B modes and K is the total number of Type B modes. This follows from the fact that if a Type B mode is not seen, then the corresponding N_i is 0. Therefore, there are only M non-zero terms in (19) and, consequently, equation (19) equals equation (18). The significance of this fact is that

$$E\left[\sum_{i=1}^M (1-d_i) N_i/T\right] = E\left[\sum_{i=1}^K (1-d_i) N_i/T\right] \\ = \sum_{i=1}^K (1-d_i) E[N_i/T] = \sum_{i=1}^K (1-d_i) \lambda_i \quad (20)$$

Therefore,

$$E[N_A/T + \sum_{i=1}^M (1-d_i) N_i/T] = \lambda_A + \sum_{i=1}^K (1-d_i) \lambda_i.$$

Thus, we may use r_p to estimate the growth potential failure rate. This estimate, of course, depends on the assigned EF's, Type A and Type B modes, and as such, is a useful management tool for evaluating reliability growth strategies.

To outline the procedure for estimating the growth potential, suppose the system is tested for a period of time T and that N failures have been observed. According to the management strategy, N_A of these failures are Type A and N_B of these failures are Type B. For the Type B modes, there will be M distinct fixes. As before, N_i is the total number of failures for the i -th Type B mode and d_i is the corresponding assigned EF. From these data, the growth potential failure rate is estimated by

$$\hat{r}_p = N_A/T + \sum_{i=1}^M (1-d_i) N_i/T \quad (21)$$

and the growth potential MTBF is estimated by

$$\hat{M}_p = [\hat{r}_p]^{-1} \quad (22)$$

To illustrate the application of the estimation procedure for the growth potential, we consider the data in the previous example. In this example, $T = 400$ and the failure rate estimate at the end of test, after the incorporation of the delayed fixes, is $r(400) = .068$. The corresponding MTBF estimate is 14.7. To estimate the maximum reliability that can be attained with this management strategy we use the calculations

$$N_A/T = .0250 \quad \text{and}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{16} (1-d_i) N_i/T = .020.$$

From equation (21), the growth potential failure rate is estimated by

$$\hat{r}_p = .0250 + .020 = .045$$

and the growth potential MTBF is estimated by

$$\hat{M}_p = [.045]^{-1} = 22.22.$$

That is, the current MTBF at $T = 400$ for the system is estimated to be 14.7, and if we continue to do business in the same fashion, it is estimated that the maximum MTBF that can be attained is 22.22.

The estimates \hat{r}_p and \hat{M}_p are, of course, subjected to statistical variation. In this example, the data were generated by computer simulation with $\lambda_A = .02$, $\lambda_B = .1$ and $K = 100$. In addition, the d_i 's for each of the 100 Type B modes were drawn from a Beta distribution with mean .7. The simulation also depended on known values of the λ_i 's. Based on these parameters, the actual growth potential for the failure rate is

$$r_p = \lambda_A + \sum_{i=1}^{100} (1-d_i) \lambda_i = .0485$$

or an MTBF of

$$M_p = 20.6$$

The MTBF value 20.6 is the true growth potential and the estimate, based on the data, is 22.2. If the requirement is an MTBF of 25, then these results indicate that this objective probably cannot be met with the current management strategy.

In practice, it is often desirable to consider the EF's (that is, the engineering effort) and their impact on the growth potential and the requirement. This can generally be accomplished effectively by considering an equivalent average EF d , instead of individual d_i 's. In this approach, we write r_p as

$$r_p = \lambda_A + (1-d) \lambda_B \quad (23)$$

and

$$M_p = [r_p]^{-1} \quad (24)$$

For example, suppose we let $\lambda_A = .02$, $\lambda_B = .1$ and desire the equivalent average EF d such that the MTBF equals 20.6 or $r_p = .0485$. This would yield a d value equal to .71, which is close to the true population mean value of .7 for the 100 d_i 's in the example. The d value would be indicative of the overall level of effectiveness which would be necessary to attain an MTBF of 20.6. If the requirement were 25, then under the same conditions, a necessary equivalent average effectiveness level would be .8.

If a necessary equivalent average effectiveness level is too high, then the other trade-offs that can be made are in terms of Type A and Type B modes. For an EF d , more modes will have to be fixed in order to raise the growth potential. In the above example $\lambda_A + \lambda_B = .12$. This is the initial failure rate for the system. For this initial failure rate and an average d of .71 we wish to have a growth potential MTBF of 25, or a failure rate of .04. This would require a management strategy such that $\lambda_A = .00832$ and $\lambda_B = .11268$. To attain this, 93.9 percent of the initial failure rate must be addressed with fixes for Type B modes. This compares with 83.3 percent of the initial failure rate when $\lambda_B = .1$.

Confidence Bounds for the Growth Potential

If the growth potential is estimated from the data, then it may be desirable to account for the statistical uncertainty of this estimate in comparison to the requirement. The statistical uncertainty can be reflected in terms of confidence bounds on the growth potential.

For convenience, in the following discussion, let

$$r = r_p, \quad \hat{r} = \hat{r}_p, \quad M = 1/r, \quad \hat{M} = 1/\hat{r}.$$

As noted earlier, $E(\hat{r}) = r$, where \hat{r} is given by equation (21). Let $\text{VAR}[\cdot]$ denote variance. Then,

Conclusions

In this paper we have established a framework in which the concept of growth potential can be clearly defined and have practical significance. With this approach the management strategy can be qualified in terms of the growth potential. Procedures were given for estimating and placing confidence intervals on the growth potential from test data. Based on these methods, trade-off and decisions can be made in regard to the appropriate management strategy to follow to attain the reliability objectives.

Biography

Dr. Larry H. Crow is Chief of the Reliability Methodology Office in the Reliability Division of the US Army Materiel Systems Analysis Activity (AMSAA), Aberdeen Proving Ground, Maryland. He obtained his PhD at Florida State University. He developed the AMSAA Reliability Growth Model which has been incorporated into military handbooks, standards and service regulations on reliability. He chaired the Tri-Service Committee to develop MIL-HDBK-189, Reliability Growth Management, and is currently Chairman of the US, UK, Canadian and Australian reliability group of the The Technical Cooperation Program (TTCP). He is a member of the American Statistical Association and Sigma Xi.

References

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$$\text{VAR}(\hat{r}) = \frac{1}{T} \left[\lambda_A + \sum_{i=1}^K (1-d_i)^2 \lambda_i \right]$$

$$\leq \frac{1}{T} \left[\lambda_A + \sum_{i=1}^K (1-d_i) \lambda_i \right] = r/T. \quad (25)$$

That is, $\text{VAR}(\hat{r})$ is bounded above by r/T . Consequently, the use of r/T for the $\text{VAR}(\hat{r})$ will yield conservative confidence bounds on r .

If

$$\sqrt{T} \left(\frac{\hat{r} - r}{\sqrt{r}} \right) \quad (26)$$

is approximately normally distributed, then $1 - \alpha$ two-sided lower and upper confidence bounds on r are given by

$$r_L = \hat{r} + c^2/2 - \sqrt{\hat{r}c^2 + c^4/4} \quad (27)$$

$$r_U = \hat{r} + c^2/2 + \sqrt{\hat{r}c^2 + c^4/4} \quad (28)$$

where

$$c = Z/\sqrt{T} \quad (29)$$

and Z is the $1 - \alpha/2$ percentile for the normal distribution. The lower and upper $1 - \alpha$ conservative confidence bounds for M are given by

$$M_L = [r_U]^{-1}, \quad M_U = [r_L]^{-1}. \quad (30)$$

Consider again the data used in the previous examples. For these data, $T = 400$ and the growth

potential failure rate estimate is $\hat{r} = .045$. The

growth potential MTBF estimate is $\hat{M} = 22.22$. For an 80 percent two-sided confidence bound on M we have $Z = 1.282$ and $c = .0641$. Using equations (27) and (28), the bounds on r are

$$r_L = .0333 \text{ and } r_U = .0608.$$

Therefore, the 80 percent confidence bounds on M are $M_L = 16.44$ and $M_U = 30.03$.

A lower bound on M is generally of particular interest. In this case, a 90 percent lower confidence bound on M is 16.44. If the MTBF requirement is below 16.44, then we would have high statistical confidence that the growth potential exists in the system to meet this objective.